

Insights into Multifactorial Perspectives: Unveiling Drug Utilization Patterns and Adverse Reactions in Osteoarthritis and Rheumatoid Arthritis Management

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the demographic distribution, treatment patterns, drug utilization, and adverse drug reactions in patients with osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. Osteoarthritis was more common in males (56.07%) than females (43.92%), while rheumatoid arthritis was more prevalent in females (67.07%) compared to males (32.96%). Osteoarthritis was most prevalent in the 51-65 years age group (45.32%), followed by 36-50 years (37.61%). Rheumatoid arthritis was predominantly found in the 51-65 years age group (89.02%), followed by 66-80 years (6.09%). For osteoarthritis, NSAIDs (44.45%) were the most prescribed, followed by analgesics (25.68%). For rheumatoid arthritis, NSAIDs (26.58%) were also common, with significant use of DMARDs (16.76%) and antacids (19.42%). Oral administration was predominant in both osteoarthritis (94.11%) and rheumatoid arthritis (95.29%). Mono-therapy was more common in osteoarthritis (79.23%) than in rheumatoid arthritis (71.11%), where combination therapy was more prevalent (28.88%). Old age (28.73%) and obesity (13.31%) were primary risk factors for osteoarthritis, while family history (45.12%) and old age (39.02%) were significant for rheumatoid arthritis. Gastric discomfort and abdominal pain were noted adverse reactions to NSAIDs, more frequent in rheumatoid arthritis patients (12.19% and 3.65%, respectively) than in osteoarthritis patients (1.86% and 0.93%). Treatment approaches and drug utilization patterns vary considerably between the two conditions, with a higher incidence of adverse reactions observed in rheumatoid arthritis. These findings underscore the need for tailored treatment strategies to optimize patient outcomes and minimize adverse effects. Further research is recommended to explore the underlying causes of these disparities and to develop more effective management protocols.

Keywords: Osteoarthritis, Rheumatoid arthritis, Drug utilization, Adverse drug reactions, Monotherapy, Combination therapy, Risk factors, Route of administration.

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Introduction

Drug utilization studies are pivotal tools in understanding the role of medications within society. They provide a solid socio-medical and economic basis for health decision-making, particularly relevant given the increasing burden of arthritis [1]. These studies promote rational use of analgesics by identifying treatment adherence problems and designing interventions to improve drug use. The importance of drug utilization studies extends to the formulation of drug policies and serves as an educational tool for drug therapy. Indiscriminate drug use often leads to unwanted adverse effects and drug interactions, complicating diagnoses and treatment processes[2]. Drug utilization studies identify issues arising from drug usage in healthcare delivery and highlight current

approaches to rational drug use. A drug utilization review is an authorized, structured, and ongoing program that reviews, analyzes, and interprets drug use patterns against pre-determined standards. The prescribing behavior of clinicians is influenced by academic literature, professional colleagues, and government regulations [3]. Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most frequent musculoskeletal disorder, primarily causing pain in one or several joints, mainly in the elderly. The disease burden is closely related to pain, leading to functional disabilities ranging from mild to severe difficulties in daily activities. Pain relief is, therefore, a central component in OA treatment, which is highly dependent on managing pain and inflammation [4]. Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA), a common type of

chronic inflammatory arthritis, significantly affects patients' quality of life, performance, and life expectancy[5]. Uncontrolled RA can lead to joint degradation and disability. It primarily affects joints, causing pain, swelling, and stiffness, but can also impact other organs. The progression of the disease increases disability and decreases the quality of life. Early therapeutic measures are crucial for improving therapeutic outcomes, although RA treatment remains largely conservative[6]. The principal goal of RA treatment is to relieve pain, thereby improving function and quality of life. Current recommendations for OA management include a combination of non-pharmacological approaches (exercise, weight reduction, physiotherapy, education programs, and lifestyle changes) and pharmacological treatments (NSAIDs, topical analgesics, and intra-articular injections). In RA management; medications include Disease Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs (DMARDs), Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), and corticosteroids. Prescribing these medications is complex, influenced by disease activity, severity, and cost[7].

Monitoring adverse events in patients taking NSAIDs and DMARDs over long periods is essential to assess the tolerability profiles of different drugs and understand how adverse events contribute to overall treatment costs, providing insights into the Pharmaco-economic status of patients [8].

Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) monitoring is critical due to variations in genetic factors, dietary habits, disease patterns, environmental factors, and drug use. In countries like India, where nutritional status and the prevalence of diseases like tuberculosis, diabetes, and hypertension vary widely, concurrent drug use can lead to significant drug-drug interactions and adverse effects. ADR monitoring provides valuable data on adverse effects and their relationship with specific drugs[9].

This proposed study aims to fill existing gaps in the literature by providing comprehensive data on drug utilization and its effects in a real-world clinical setting[10]. The current study seeks to enhance the understanding of current practices and promote more effective and safer drug use in the treatment of osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis [11].

Materials & Methods

This study was conducted over one year, from December 2016 to November 2017, in the Orthopedic Department at Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raichur.

Ethical committee approval was obtained prior to the commencement of the study. This comprehensive methodology ensures a thorough

evaluation of drug utilization patterns, adverse drug reactions, and treatment outcomes in patients with OA and RA, providing valuable insights for optimizing therapeutic strategies [12].

Study Design: This is a prospective observational study designed to evaluate drug utilization patterns, adverse drug reactions (ADRs), and treatment outcomes in patients with osteoarthritis (OA) and rheumatoid arthritis (RA)[13].

Study Population

Inclusion Criteria

- Diagnosed cases of arthritis visiting the orthopedic department.
- Patients of either sex aged between 18-80 years.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients below 18 years of age
- Patients diagnosed with Gastro esophageal reflux disease and peptic ulcer.
- Pregnant and lactating women
- Patients with cardiovascular problems
- Patients with significant neurological deficits
- Terminally ill patients

Data Collection

Patient Recruitment and Consent: Patients satisfying the inclusion criteria were identified and recruited during their visits to the orthopedic department. Informed consent was obtained from all participants [14].

Data Recording: Information regarding patient demographics, ADRs, suspected drugs, and concomitantly administered drugs was recorded using the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) Adverse Drug Reaction reporting form. Data were collected as per a designed case record form (CRF)[15].

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive Statistics: Demographic and baseline variables were summarized using descriptive statistics.

Continuous Variables: These were summarized using mean (\pm SD). Parametric data were analyzed using the Student's t-test.

Categorical Variables: These were analyzed using appropriate statistical tests, such as chi-square tests.

All statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. This comprehensive methodology ensures a thorough evaluation of drug utilization patterns, adverse drug reactions, and treatment outcomes in patients with OA and RA, providing valuable insights for optimizing therapeutic strategies[16].

Results

Case sheets of five hundred and ten patients with diagnosis of Osteoarthritis and Rheumatoid arthritis were evaluated and data was analyzed as follow.

Table 1: Details of Gender Distribution

Gender Distribution	No of patient	Percentage
Male	267	52.35%
Female	243	47.64%
Total	510	100

Table 2: Details of Gender Distribution in Osteoarthritis and Rheumatoid Arthritis

Age Distribution (Yrs)	Patient	No of Patient	Percentage
20-35	OA	44	10.28%
	RA	0	0.00%
36-50	OA	161	37.61%
	RA	4	4.87%
51-65	OA	194	45.32%
	RA	73	89.02%
66-80	OA	29	6.77%
	RA		6.09%
Total	OA	428	100
	RA	82	100

Table 3: Details of Age Distribution of Osteoarthritis Patient

Gender Distribution	Patient	No of patient	Percentage
Male	OA	240	56.07%
	RA	27	32.96%
Female	OA	188	43.92%
	RA	55	67.07%
Total	OA	428	100
	RA	82	100

Figure 1: Details of Class of Drugs in Osteoarthritis

Figure 1 Shows class of drugs prescribed for osteoarthritis, NSAIDS (44.45 %) are the drug of choice for osteoarthritis patient followed by analgesics (25.68 %) antacids (12.28 %) and adjuvant (10.15 %).

Figure 2: Class of Drugs Prescribed in RA

Figure 2 Shows details of class of drugs prescribed in rheumatoid arthritis, NSAIDS (26.58 %) are the drug of choice for rheumatoid arthritis patient followed by DMARDS (16.76 %) analgesics (14.11 %) antacids (19.42 %) and adjuvant (14.31 %)

Table 4: Details of Route of Administration of Drugs in Osteoarthritis

Route	Patient	Drugs	Percentage
Oral	OA	1103	94.11%
	RA	466	95.29%
Injectable	OA	50	04.26%
	RA	17	03.47%
Topical	OA	19	01.62%
	RA	06	01.22%
Total	OA	1172	100
	RA	489	100

Table 5: Approach to Treatment in Osteoarthritis

Approach to Treatment	Patient	Total No Of Drugs	Percentage
Monotherapy	OA	847	79.23%
	RA	293	71.11%
Combination Therapy	OA	222	20.76%
	RA	119	28.88%
Total	OA	1069	100
	RA	412	100

Table 6: Details of Risk Factors for Osteoarthritis

Risk Factors	Total No of Patient(N=428)	Percentage
Family History	46	10.74 %
	37	45.12 %
Old Age	123	28.73 %
	32	39.02 %
Obesity	57	13.31 %
	12	14.63 %

Table 7: Details of Class of NSAIDs Prescribed in Osteoarthritis

NSAIDS	Drug	No Prescription (N=557), (N=132)	Percentage
Preferential Cox-2 Inhibitors	Diclofenac	142	25.49%
		44	33.33 %
	Aceclofenac	183	32.85 %
		40	30.30 %
	Nimesulide	62	11.01 %
		17	12.08 %
Propionic Acid Derviatives	Ibuprofen	22	03.94 %
		5	03.78 %
Enolic Acid Derviatives	Piroxicam	36	06.46 %
		5	03.78 %
Acetaminophen	Paracetamol	112	20.10 %
		21	15.90 %

Table 8: Details of Corticosteroids used for OA and RA

Corticosteroids	No. of Prescriptions Osteoarthritis (N=428)	Percentage	No. of Prescriptions Rheumatoid Arthritis (N=82)	Percentage
Prednisolone	40	09.34 %	25	30.48%
Deflazacort	22	05.14 %	10	12.19%
Dexamethasone	25	05.84 %	8	09.75%

Table 9: Details of Combination Therapy

	Combination Therapy	No. of Prescription	Percentage
Osteoarthritis (N=428)	Aceclofenac +Paracetamol	51	11.91%
	Diclofenac +Paracetamol	25	05.84%
	Tramadol +Paracetamol	27	06.30%
	Calcium+ Vit D3	61	14.25 %
	Multivitamins	58	13.55 %
	Combination Therapy	No. of Prescription	Percentage
Rheumatoid Arthritis (N=82)	Aceclofenac +Paracetamol	11	13.41 %
	Diclofenac +Paracetamol	8	09.75 %
	Tramadol +Paracetamol	3	03.65 %
	Dmards+Dmards	49	59.75 %
	Calcium+ Vit D3	22	26.82 %
	Multivitamins	48	58.53 %

Table 10: Adverse Drug Reaction with usage of Nsaids

Adverse Drug Reaction	Symptoms	No. of Prescription	Percentage	
Osteoarthritis (N=428)	Total= 23 (05.37%)	Gastric Discomfort	8	01.86 %
		Abdominal Pain	4	00.93 %
		Nausea	1	00.23 %
		Vomiting	5	01.16 %
		Skin Rashes	3	00.70 %
		Loose Stools	1	00.23 %
		Dizziness	1	00.23 %
	Symptoms	No. of Prescription	Percentage	
Rheumatoid Arthritis (N=82)	Total= 18 (21.95 %)	Gastric Discomfort	10	12.19 %
		Abdominal Pain	3	03.65 %
		Nausea	1	01.21 %
		Vomiting	1	01.21 %
		Skin Rashes	2	02.43 %
		Loose Stools	0	0
		Dizziness	1	01.21 %

This detailed analysis provides insights into the patterns of drug utilization, gender and age distribution, preferred drug classes, routes of administration, treatment approaches, risk factors, and adverse drug reactions in patients with osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis [17]. The results highlight the prevalence of certain medications and adverse effects, which can inform future strategies for optimizing treatment and improving patient outcomes [18].

Discussion

Gender Distribution: The gender distribution analysis reveals a higher overall number of males (52.35%) compared to females (47.64%). Specifically, osteoarthritis affects more males (56.07%) than females (43.92%), whereas rheumatoid arthritis predominantly affects females (67.07%) compared to males (32.96%).

This gender disparity suggests that while osteoarthritis may have a slight male predominance, rheumatoid arthritis is significantly more common among females [19,20]. These findings align with existing literature that reports a higher incidence of rheumatoid arthritis in women, potentially due to hormonal and genetic factors.

Age Distribution: The age distribution data shows that osteoarthritis is most prevalent among individuals aged 51-65 years (45.32%), followed by those aged 36-50 years (37.61%). In contrast, rheumatoid arthritis is overwhelmingly prevalent in the 51-65 years age group (89.02%), with a secondary prevalence in the 66-80 years age group (6.09%). The high prevalence of both conditions in older age groups underscores the role of aging as a significant risk factor, particularly for osteoarthritis, which is associated with the degeneration of joint tissues over time [21].

Class of Drugs Prescribed: For osteoarthritis, NSAIDs (44.45%) are the most commonly prescribed class of drugs, followed by analgesics (25.68%), antacids (12.28%), and adjuvants (10.15%). In rheumatoid arthritis, NSAIDs (26.58%) are also prevalent, but DMARDs (16.76%) and a higher usage of antacids (19.42%) indicate a more aggressive treatment approach aimed at modifying disease progression. The preference for NSAIDs in both conditions reflects their efficacy in managing pain and inflammation, while the higher use of DMARDs in rheumatoid arthritis highlights the necessity of disease-modifying therapies in managing this autoimmune condition [22,23].

Route of Administration: Oral administration is the predominant route for both osteoarthritis (94.11%) and rheumatoid arthritis (95.29%), followed by injectable and topical applications. The preference for oral medication is likely due to its

ease of administration and patient compliance. However, the use of injectable, though minimal, indicates cases where more immediate or targeted drug delivery is necessary [24].

Treatment Approaches: Monotherapy is more common in osteoarthritis (79.23%) compared to combination therapy (20.76%). Conversely, rheumatoid arthritis treatment is less reliant on mono-therapy (71.11%), with a higher incidence of combination therapy (28.88%) [25]. This difference suggests that rheumatoid arthritis often requires a more comprehensive treatment approach to manage the complex autoimmune aspects of the disease effectively [26].

Risk Factors: Old age (28.73%) and obesity (13.31%) are significant risk factors for osteoarthritis, while family history (45.12%) and old age (39.02%) are predominant risk factors for rheumatoid arthritis. The identification of these risk factors is critical for early diagnosis and intervention strategies. For instance, weight management and lifestyle modifications can be crucial in preventing or delaying the onset of osteoarthritis [27,28].

Class of NSAIDs Used: Aceclofenac (32.85%), Diclofenac (25.49%), and Paracetamol (20.10%) are the most commonly used NSAIDs in osteoarthritis, while Diclofenac (33.33%), Aceclofenac (30.30%), and Paracetamol (15.90%) are preferred in rheumatoid arthritis. The frequent use of these medications highlights their effectiveness in managing pain and inflammation in both conditions [29].

Use of Corticosteroids: Prednisolone is more commonly used in rheumatoid arthritis (30.48%) than in osteoarthritis (9.34%), reflecting the need for stronger anti-inflammatory action in the former due to its autoimmune nature.

Combination Therapy: Combination therapy involving Aceclofenac and Paracetamol (11.91%) is preferred for osteoarthritis, while DMARDs combination therapy (59.75%) is more common in rheumatoid arthritis, followed by Aceclofenac and Paracetamol (13.41%). This indicates that while pain management is central to osteoarthritis treatment, rheumatoid arthritis requires a more complex therapeutic regimen to control disease progression and symptoms [30,31].

Adverse Drug Reactions: Gastric discomfort (1.86%) and abdominal pain (0.93%) are noted adverse reactions in osteoarthritis patients using NSAIDs, whereas these adverse effects are significantly higher in rheumatoid arthritis patients (gastric discomfort 12.19%, abdominal pain 3.65%). This suggests a higher susceptibility to gastrointestinal side effects in rheumatoid arthritis

patients, likely due to the higher and more prolonged use of NSAIDs [32,33,34].

Conclusion

This detailed analysis provides comprehensive insights into the treatment patterns, demographic distribution, drug utilization, and adverse effects associated with osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. The findings emphasize the importance of personalized treatment approaches, considering the differing prevalence, risk factors, and treatment responses. These insights can inform future research and clinical strategies aimed at optimizing treatment protocols and improving patient outcomes in managing these chronic conditions.

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